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- Genetics & Medicine
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- Literature
- Proteins
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- Taxonomy
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- Three outdated browsers (1000 Genomes, dbGaP Data, and Get-REM) retire in April 2022. Data available in 28 Oct
- [The Genome Data Viewer \(GDV\) is now available](#)
- NCBI will assign 64-bit numeric GIs to November 15th. Update affected software! 27 Oct
- As announced last month, NCBI will
- Nov 3 Webinar: dbGaP submission improvements and GaPTools 25 Oct
- Attention dbGaP submitters! Join us November 3, 2021 at 12PM US eastern

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- Genomes & Maps
- Homology
- Literature
- Proteins
- Sequence Analysis
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Low-gluten, nontransgenic wheat engineered with CRISPR/Cas9.

Sánchez-León S, et al. Plant Biotechnol J. 2018.

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Coeliac disease is an autoimmune disorder triggered in genetically predisposed individuals by the ingestion of gluten proteins from wheat, b ...

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Intestinal absorption of the wheat allergen **gliadin** in rats.

Yokooji T, et al. Allergol Int. 2019. PMID: 30559050

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Immunoblotting showed that most **gliadin** was absorbed in intact form. When the **gliadin** fraction

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